

THE ROLE OF THE INTERNET IN A GLOBALIZING WORLD

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ABSTRACT

This article Today, the ideological landscape of the world is becoming very complicated, and it has become clear that the best way to have a strong influence in it is to occupy the position of a major information distributor, regardless of the amount of money required. It is not difficult for even ordinary people to notice that there is an "information war" going on in the world. For example, let's say that brochures and films glorifying the lifestyle and value system of a foreign country are being distributed. Naturally, such information has an impact on the formation of a certain social opinion in society.

Today, the ideological landscape of the world has become very complicated. It became clear that the best way to have a strong influence was to occupy the position of a major information distributor, regardless of the amount of money required. It is not difficult for even ordinary people to notice that there is an "information war" going on in the world. For example, let's say that brochures and films glorifying the lifestyle and value system of a foreign country are being distributed. Naturally, such information does not fail to influence the formation of a certain social opinion in the society.

The processes of post-industrial revolution, informationization and globalization, unfortunately, have created categories that seek to satisfy their material interests and needs, have almost lost their national image, and are ready to use any idea for their goals. Such a negative situation will

not fail to affect the population of our country, especially our youth. In order to eliminate this threat, it is necessary to fight consistently, using all possible means. Today, even a small message directed against human spirituality, seemingly insignificant at first glance, can take strength from the intensity of globalization in the information world and cause enormous damage, which is invisible, but the damage cannot be compensated by anything.

Therefore, now that every information has the characteristic of knowing no borders, many people should think about protecting the integrity of the spiritual world of the young generation, whose consciousness and worldview are just being formed. The problem will not be solved by restricting the Internet or banning access to information. In today's conditions where it is difficult to imagine life without media,

the Internet is becoming the main source of information for young people. However, there are some shows and sites related to Western culture that are completely unethical. It is clear that such information has a negative impact on the behavior and outlook of our youth. It is permissible to mention one more point at this point. In our opinion, the fact that "Oynai Jahon" is full of serials is not a positive thing. Because the fact that young people spend most of their time watching these series does not affect the quality of education. By the way, the shallow content of the information and information published on the pages of newspapers and magazines also has a negative impact on the thinking of our youth.

Any information obtained from the Internet can be used as a weapon. Because in the present era, the Internet, which is called an information tool, has its own characteristics, the most important of which is its wide range of applications in the modern world, and its application is unparalleled. The information obtained from the Internet is also a tool that gives each person answers to their necessary questions and new ideas about these answers.

If we consider information as a weapon, how it can affect human psychology:

1. In a narrow sense, a person receives information based on his own point of view and worldview;
2. If a person has the ability to filter information, he immediately sorts it and adapts it to himself;
3. Monitors information reserves depending on the size and content of information;
4. Checking all the information obtained from the Internet to prove that it is correct

or incorrect information, it is possible to organize an information base on the topics that interest him;

5. In organizing these, human thinking is the most important and has a wide range of possibilities

Nowadays, in the higher education system, students are trying to get most of the information from the Internet. The Internet has become the most popular and fastest means of information distribution. In our country, the majority of Internet users, including social networks, are young people. The Internet system is being used for various purposes, for getting to know each other, getting information, exchanging information, learning a language, and spending time from idleness. This leads to a diversity of purposes for receiving and transmitting information. As a result, we can see that students unknowingly get involved in sites and social networks with various unhealthy views.

It is known that the freedom of conscience and belief, the rights of representatives of different nationalities are widely guaranteed in our country, and the atmosphere of religious tolerance is being strengthened. Today, representatives of more than 130 nationalities live peacefully and harmoniously in our country. Spreading extremist ideas that cause discord among them is not allowed in Uzbekistan at all. This is the aspect that makes us superior to other countries.

As an example, it should be noted that the illegal preparation, storage, importation or distribution of religious materials for the purpose of dissemination into the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is committed after the application of administrative punishment for such acts, a fine in the amount of one hundred to two hundred

times the minimum monthly salary or shall be punished by correctional labor for up to three years. Based on this, it can be said that the safety of the individual, society and the state is at the root of such measures. In recent years, the game "Critical Whale", i.e. "Blue Whale", which has become popular among young people, is playing on the Internet.

Бугунги кунга келиб и is a game that is spreading and has claimed the lives of hundreds of teenagers. How much can a game cost a person's life?

This game can't be downloaded from playmarket because it's a game to be played on social media especially v contact. The premise of the game is that you will be given 50 tasks, after completing all of them, the reward will be your own death. To start the game, you need to join a group called Cynical Whale. The main participants of the group are schoolchildren. All the information in the group has a strong psychological effect on a person and makes him depressed. Game quests arrive at 4:20 a.m. every morning. The first task is to cut off a hand and draw a picture of a whale on it, and the last task is to commit suicide. Apparently, a 14-15-year-old teenager,

who did not commit suicide, is forced to commit suicide by intimidation. Philip Liss, who was believed to be the leader of the game group, was mentally ill and was sentenced to 1 year in prison for the game he created. He gathered more than 300 thousand subscribers to his group. The reason why the group is called blue whale is because whales throw themselves ashore due to depression. This game has claimed the lives of more than 230 teenagers.

The main reason for the above cases is the lack of information culture among young people. On the other hand, it is certainly impossible to enumerate the useful aspects of the Internet. Why is it possible to zoom in on a distance, get scientific and creative activity, or get quick information in the global space, etc. It's no secret that all of them are done through internet networks. Therefore, every member of the society must have an objective conclusion about any source of information when using the Internet. After all, objectivity is in our consciousness, in the purity of our worldview and the harmony of our national mentality and values with our way of thinking, which is the driving force behind its purity.

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